

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

Sample distribution, transport and conservation

**Version 1
May/2020**

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Sample distribution, transport and conservation

A. Description

Sample distribution, transport and conservation in FED-AMR project, according to the compartment and methodologies to be used (for WP2, WP3 and WP4), ensuring harmonization.

B. Samples distribution, transport and conservation

Sample	Compartment No.	Quantity	Type of sample	Conservation for Microbiology (WP2, WP3) [cultivable bacteria and MICs to be performed in each country]	Conservation of sample for Genomics (WP2) [DNA extraction to be performed by each country]	Transportation for Genomics (WP2)	Conservation for Quantification (WP4)	Transportation for Quantification (WP4)	Used in WP	
Faeces	<i>Faeces (pigs)</i>	C1	- Cdif : 6 pools of 5 samples each, 5g each sample - Others : Pool 30 samples, 5g each sample;	30 single fecal samples combined to a composite sample per barn (1 pool)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	freeze for WP4	WP4.4: 50 g, freeze, 200ml dark PP or PET bottles; WP4.7: 250 g, freeze, PET bottles	WP2, WP3, WP4.4, WP4.7
	<i>Faeces (farmers)</i>	C9	- Others and Cdif : 1 pool of 4 samples (4 persons)	Normal human faeces sampling	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (faeces)	see above (faeces)	WP2, WP3, WP4.4, WP4.7
	<i>Faeces (wild animals)</i>	C11	- Others and Cdif : Pool 10 samples, 5g each sample, by animal species	Single fecal samples combined to 10 composite sample per barn (10 pools)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (faeces)	see above (faeces)	WP2, WP3, WP4.4, WP4.7
Manure	C2	1.5 Kg		Composite sample	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	freeze for WP4	WP4.3: 50 g, freeze, 200ml dark PP or PET bottles; WP4.7: 250 g, freeze, PET bottles	WP2, WP3, WP4.3, WP4.7
Soil	C3	1.5 Kg		Ten equidistant single soil subsamples are combined to build a composite soil sample "representative" for the analyzed field (10x10m)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	dry < 40°C; sieve < 2mm; freeze for WP4	WP4.5: 25 g, freeze, 200ml dark PP or PET bottles; WP4.6: 100g, 4°C, plastic containers; WP4.7: 300-400 g, 4°C, PET bags	WP2, WP3, WP4.5, WP4.6, WP4.7
Crops	C4	2.0 Kg		Leaves + stalks + ears + washed roots (not mixed)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	WP4.7: keep in a dark, cool place.; no need of refrigeration	WP4.7: appr. 400 g, PET bags, no need of refrigeration	WP2, WP4.7

Sample	Compartment No.	Quantity	Type of sample	Conservation for Microbiology (WP2, WP3) [cultivable bacteria and MICs to be performed in each country]	Conservation of sample for Genomics (WP2) [DNA extraction to be performed by each country]	Transportation for Genomics (WP2)	Conservation for Quantification (WP4)	Transportation for Quantification (WP4)	Used in WP	
Water	<i>Field drainage</i>	C5	5L in separated bottles	Superficial water (sampling by direct immersion; about 20 cm deep)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	WP4.2: 150 ml, freeze; WP 4.7: 50 ml, 4 °C	WP4.2: 150 ml, freeze, 200ml dark PP or PET bottles; WP 4.7: 50 ml, 4°C, PET bottles: before collection on site, each of the tubes must be acidified in the lab with two drops of conc. HNO3 (for trace metal analysis grade)	WP2, WP4.2, WP4.7
	<i>River water</i>	C6	5L in separated bottles	Superficial water (sampling by direct immersion; about 20 cm deep)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (water)	see above (water)	WP2, WP4.2, WP4.7
	<i>Drinking water</i>	C7	5L in separated bottles	Drinking water (mains water).	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (water)	see above (water)	WP2, WP4.2, WP4.7
	<i>Groundwater</i>	C7	5L in separated bottles	Well/borehole (deep sampling method; 2m to 5m deep)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (water)	see above (water)	WP2, WP4.2, WP4.7
	<i>WTP influent</i>	C10	5L in separated bottles (200mL for Cdif)	Superficial water (sampling by direct immersion; about 20 cm deep)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (water)	see above (water)	WP2, WP3, WP4.2, WP4.7
	<i>WTP effluent</i>	C10	5L in separated bottles (200mL for Cdif)	Superficial water (sampling by direct immersion; about 20 cm deep)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (water)	see above (water)	WP2, WP3, WP4.2, WP4.7
	<i>WTP sedimentation tank</i>	C10	5L in separated bottles (200mL for Cdif)	Superficial water from the sedimentation tank (sampling by direct immersion; about 20 cm deep)	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	see above (water)	see above (water)	WP2, WP3, WP4.7
	<i>WTP sewage sludge</i>	C10	1.0 Kg	Five equidistant single sludge subsamples are combined to build a composite sludge sample	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	WP4.7: keep in a dark, cool place.; no need of refrigeration	WP4.7: appr. 400 g, PET bags, no need of refrigeration	WP2, WP3, WP4.7
Feed	C8	1.5 Kg	The fraction should be taken from a larger volume in such a way that the determinations will represent the mean value of the characteristic of the entire sample	0 to 5°C/ processed in 18h due to eDNA	0 to 5°C until extraction	DNA at -80°C	WP4.7: keep in a dark, cool place.; no need of refrigeration	WP4.7: appr. 400 g, PET bags, no need of refrigeration	WP2, WP4.7	